

Explore activities management to support the care and education of public preschools

Thuan Van Pham¹, LongAn Dang Nguyen²

¹National Academy of Education Management, Hanoi, Vietnam

²Ho Chi Minh City College of Economics, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 13, 2024

Revised Jul 21, 2025

Accepted Sep 30, 2025

Keywords:

Children

Managing activities

Public preschool

Quality of care

Quality of education

ABSTRACT

This study aims to explore the contents of the management of support activities for care and education, as well as the impacts of these activities on improving the quality of support and care for children in public preschools in Thu Duc city, Vietnam. To achieve this purpose, qualitative and quantitative research methods were used through the evaluation of relevant documents. At the same time, a survey of 175 people, including managers, teachers, and parents of students, was conducted. The research results show that although the management of support activities for care and education for children in public preschools has achieved some good results, it still reveals many limitations that need to be identified and addressed with appropriate solutions. Based on the assessment of the current situation and identification of the causes, this study has proposed suitable solutions to improve the quality of support activities for care and education for children in public schools in Thu Duc city.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

LongAn Dang Nguyen

Scientific Education, Ho Chi Minh City College of Economics

No 33 Vinh Vien Street, Ward 2, District 10, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

Email: longnda@kthcm.edu.vn

1. INTRODUCTION

Care and education for the young generation are always the top concerns of society because of their particular importance to the development of each person, each community, and every country in a civilized society. All care and education activities are carried out to contribute to improving the quality of education, for the sake of people, and the development of the country. The value of an individual, a community, and a country depends mainly on the quality of education. Therefore, educational care, especially public educational institutions, always strive to constantly improve the quality of care and education activities and takes many measures to support the operation best.

In the national education system of Vietnam, preschool education always keeps a position and its role is particularly important. The Communist Party of Vietnam recognized the importance of this level of education. "For preschool education, helping children develop physical, emotional, understanding, aesthetic, forming the first elements of personality education, well-prepared children to enter first grade. Complete the universalization of preschool education for five-year-old children by 2021, improve the quality of universalization in the following years, and exempt tuition fees by 2030. Develop quality preschool education under five years old suitable to McGowan conditions and maintain the education" [1].

To ensure quality in the nurturing, care, and education of preschool children, the role of management is required. Managing child care, nurturing, and education activities at preschools is the impact of managers on teachers and children with the effective support of social forces to carry out the activities.

The process of caring, nurturing, and educating children to form and develop comprehensively the child's personality according to the training objectives of the preschool. Child care, nurturing, and education activities are typical activities of preschools, conducted regularly and with specific management plans for each of these activities. "It is very necessary to help preschool managers and teachers understand the concept, necessity, content, methods, forms and procedures of the steps to evaluate the implementation of the child care and education plan in preschools" [2].

Thu Duc city (Vietnam) was established in 2020 based on merging three districts: District 2, District 9, and Thu Duc district. Since its establishment, as a young city, Thu Duc city has had many activities to ensure the quality of education at all levels in general and public preschools in particular. With that quality assurance, the management measures to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in the city have gradually stabilized the situation by encouraging some remarkable results. However, with a newly established city, restructuring the activities of socio-economic sectors requires measures to handle. For the education sector, in addition to the achieved results, operational management measures ensure the quality of care and education for children at public preschools in Thu Duc city is also facing significant challenges. Therefore, it is necessary at this time to have practical support measures to further improve the quality of child care and education at public preschools in the city. Focusing study on this activity helps educational managers have initial tools in management activities and helps improve the quality of education in public kindergartens in Thu Duc city.

From a research perspective and activity, according to the assessment of the Thu Duc city Department of Education, up to now, there has not been any research focusing on clarifying the current situation of support activity child care and education support activities and this activity in public schools in particular as well as the management of child care and support activities in public preschools since the establishment of Thu Duc city. This is the first study to explore the content of management of child care and education support activities, as well as the impact of these activities on improving the quality of child care support at public preschools in Thu Duc city; at the same time, the proposed solutions are considered the contribution of this study. Thus, the novelty of the study is to discover the role, importance and necessity of supporting activities for child care and education in general and the management of child care and education activities in public preschools in particular, as well as the results that these activities bring. By surveying the current situation, combined with theoretical studies, the basic contents of managing child care and education activities in public preschools have been systematized, which can help leaders of public preschools improve the quality of education and child care.

To clarify the issues of the topic, the research focuses on answering the following questions:

- i) Can you evaluate the quality of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city?
- ii) What is the actual situation of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city?
- iii) What is the current status of conditions for quality assurance of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city?
- iv) Causes of the actual situation of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city?

To achieve the purpose of the study, a survey method has been implemented, the results will be compared and contrasted with previous related studies. The survey and comparison results will allow the author to have accurate judgments and assessments, thereby providing appropriate solutions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Supporting activities

The term "support" has many different meanings. In each specific field, there will be an explanation related to that field. According to the Vietnamese Dictionary, the term "support" refers to the act of providing assistance or help to others. It is conceptually related to notions of mutual aid and complementary assistance. In common usage, the word "support" implies cooperation and timely assistance among individuals, such as helping friends or assisting teammates when necessary [3]. Support activities are actions performed by a non-profit organization that are not program services. Support activities often include fundraising, management, general activities and member development activities [4]. With these views, "support" is understood as mutual assistance in daily activities.

Support activities are activities within a company that support the entire company by providing infrastructure or inputs that enable critical activities to continue [5], [6]. Support activities are understood as actions to help a person or a group of people in difficult circumstances. This act of help is expressed in material, and spiritual [7]. With these views, "support" is understood as mutual support for development.

With the previous explanation, “support” activities are understood as the help of a specific person or group of people with a higher position in society to a weaker person or group of people to improve problems arising for the weaker group. Support is mutual support for development. At the same time, support is the interaction between two parties to achieve specific goals in daily activities. In this study, the word “support” is understood as the actions of the dominant people (teachers, staff) in the school to help the disadvantaged people (children) achieve the set educational goals.

2.2. Activities to the child of care and education

In Vietnam’s education system, preschool education is the first and most important level that needs the attention of the whole society. In particular, care and education activities are given special attention. Child care and education activities in preschools are stipulated in Article 24 of the “Preschool regulations”, issued together with the consolidated document [8]: i) child care and education are carried out through activities according to the regulations of the preschool education program; ii) child care and education activities include nutritional care, sleep care, hygiene care, health and safety care; and iii) child education activities include play activities, learning activities, labor activities, and festival and holiday activities.

In addition, the “Preschool regulations” also have specific provisions for some special cases such as: i) inclusive education activities for children with disabilities in schools and kindergartens are implemented according to regulations on education for children with disabilities issued by the Ministry of Education and Training; ii) the nurturing, care, and education of children are also carried out through propaganda and dissemination of scientific knowledge on nurturing, caring for and educating children to parents and the community; and iii) care and education activities must take place in an absolutely safe environment.

Thus, with the viewpoints, the care and education of preschool children is to prepare the necessary conditions for children to enter primary school. The goal of the program is to comprehensively develop the social, emotional, cognitive and physical needs of children to build a solid and broad foundation for lifelong learning and happiness. All social forces must join hands to fulfill the requirements set out to absolutely ensure the care and education of young children.

2.3. Activities to support the care and education of preschool children

Activities of caring, nurturing, and educating children determine the psychological and personality development of children. This is an activity that puts many requirements on the content, methods, and forms of knowledge acquisition, skills, techniques, and moral and personality training [9]. Therefore, children will face certain difficulties and need to be guided and supported to fulfill those requirements [10], [11].

To do this, teachers, in addition to organizing and controlling educational and teaching activities, orienting children's self-study and self-training activities, also need to have support measures, such as accompanying, following monitor, and promptly detecting the unique difficulties of each child. It is essential to coordinate with educational stakeholders both within and outside the school to develop and implement appropriate measures that effectively support children in achieving positive learning and training outcomes. In addition, mental support care for young children also needs to be done regularly. In some cases, young children with special circumstances and psychological needs need to be consulted by psychological experts.

The process of supporting the care and education of preschool children is not only psychological counseling for each specific child when they have difficulties in life, but also includes preventive activities, for all children. Schools play a crucial role in creating a supportive environment that fosters children's personality development and enhances their cognitive awareness, essential life skills, emotional balance, and psychological well-being [12], [13]. Preschool and kindergarten teachers, in addition to educating and teaching to develop psychological and personality for young children, the teachers have the additional job of “advising and supporting” to help children achieve the purpose of education and teaching [14]. All these care and education support activities require close links between schools, families, and related social forces.

3. METHOD

3.1. Questionnaire

To have a practical basis to accurately evaluate the contents related to the management of care and education support activities for children in public preschools in Thu Duc city, the author has designed the questionnaires intended to answer the following essential content: i) evaluation of the quality of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city; ii) the actual situation of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city; iii) current status of conditions for quality assurance of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city; and iv) causes of the actual situation of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city.

The contents have covered all the research contents. The survey of these contents allows for a full and comprehensive assessment of the activities to support child care and education in public preschools. At the same time, find out the causes of limitations and weaknesses; from there, we can propose appropriate management solutions for the young, to improve the quality of child care and education support activities of Thu Duc city in the future.

3.2. Object and method of survey

The purpose of the survey is to survey the current situation of managing activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city. With the collected results and the theoretical basis, the topic proposes appropriate management measures to improve the quality of management activities to ensure the quality of child care and education in public preschools. The survey was conducted for administrators and teachers in 10 public preschools in Thu Duc city. The subjects of the survey are administrators (principals, vice principals), teachers, and parents of pupils of public preschools in Thu Duc city. The number survey is 175 people, including 20 managers (principal and vice principal), 75 teachers, and 80 parents of pupils. With a diverse survey audience, a sufficient number of surveys will allow for relatively accurate assessments and evaluations.

This study was ethically approved by the Thu Duc city Office of Education and Training, Ho Chi Minh City Department of Education and Training. Before data collection, all participants obtained written informed consent. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines set by the Ministry of Education and Training of Vietnam. The sampling technique used was probability sampling, specifically simple random sampling. Simple random sampling is a sampling technique commonly used in quantitative research involving survey instruments. It is generally considered appropriate for homogeneous and evenly distributed populations. This method ensures that every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected, making the selection process completely random. The simple random sampling method can give good results because there is not much difference between preschools in Thu Duc city. However, to properly assess the current status of child care and education support activities in Thu Duc city with this number, it is not guaranteed that there will be enough time and other conditions to do so. Therefore, this is also a limitation of the topic and it takes time, as well as other objective and subjective factors to perfect the topic in the future.

The survey is in the form of a questionnaire with many answer options. There are also many open-ended questions to find out more research information. There are many questions asked on the same topic and are linked, providing more flexibility and more data for analysis. Using questionnaires to survey through software that uses statistical techniques, advanced tables to synthesize, and analyze survey data. Based on the analytical framework, the study aims to determine the validity, reliability, and statistical significance of the data, including the capacity to analyze multiple variables. To achieve this, diverse forms of data are collected to supplement, revise, and further develop the research framework, such as participants' attitudes, opinions, beliefs, values, behaviors, and practices. In-depth interviews with managers and teachers in public preschools in Thu Duc city were conducted to learn more about the research issue. Screening of responses is necessary to find focused responses that address the research problem.

After collecting questionnaires from survey subjects, check the validity and invalidity of the questionnaires. The validity of the response is determined by the content and the difference from other survey subjects. Next, using statistical methods, using Excel and statistical package for social science (SPSS) software to process data in the form of percentages and average scores to assess the status quo.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. The position and role of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education

According to the Education Law (2019), Article 23, "The position, role, and objectives of preschool education" stipulates as: "Preschool education is the first level of education in the national education system, placing the foundation for the comprehensive development of Vietnamese people, to nurture, care for and educate children from 3 months to 6 years old. Pre-school education aims to comprehensively develop children physically, emotionally, intellectually, and aesthetically, form the first element of personality, and prepare children for first grade" [11].

To achieve the goals as stipulated in the Law on Education, child care and education are the top tasks in preschool education. This activity is carried out daily through physical education activities, fun activities, eating, and sleeping care activities, especially children's diets, food hygiene and safety, and healthy eating habits, daily nutrition is of great concern [15], [16]. The quality of food hygiene and safety has the effect of enhancing and protecting children's health, helping children to develop in a harmonious and balanced manner, and creating good conditions for children to participate in educational activities, which is

the first foundation for children's health the formation and development of the child's personality [17]. For these activities to take place smoothly and achieve results, it is necessary to ensure the quality of child care and education quality [18], [19].

Activities to ensure the quality of child care, nurturing and education in schools directly determine children's psychological and personality development [20]. This is an activity that puts many requirements on the content, methods, and forms of knowledge acquisition, skills, techniques, and moral and personality training. children will face certain difficulties and need guidance and support to fulfill those requirements. To do this, preschool teachers, in addition to organizing and controlling educational and teaching activities, orienting children's self-study and self-training activities, also need to accompany, closely monitor, and promptly detect each child's unique difficulties; from there, coordinate with educational forces inside and outside the school to find appropriate measures and ways to help children perform well in learning and training activities.

4.2. Content on quality assurance of early childhood education care

Several studies [21]–[24] believe that supporting educational activities requires specific regulations of the education sector and of the school itself. According to previous studies [25]–[27], for support activities to achieve good results, it is necessary to ensure adequate conditions for facilities, financial resources, teachers, and staff. From previous comments, research, and assessments, to ensure the quality of child care and education, early childhood care and education must well implement the following contents.

The nameplate of the unit should be written according to the type of license, clearly stating the license number and the issuing unit. The unit nameplate must clearly state the name and address. In addition, the school's brand identity logo can be inserted. In addition, make sure not to accept more than the number of children under the license category. According to current preschool education regulations, the maximum class size in kindergartens is defined by age group as: i) for children aged 3–4 years, up to 25 students per class; ii) for children aged 4–5 years, up to 30 students; and iii) for children aged 5–6 years, up to 35 students. Each preschool institution is permitted to enroll no more than 70 children in total.

Pursuant to Clauses 4 and 5, Article 14 of the regulations issued under Circular No. 49/2021/TT-BGDĐT by the Ministry of Education and Training, each nursery group or kindergarten class must have at least two qualified teachers. Educational institutions are required to maintain sufficient teaching staff and regularly update the teacher roster in accordance with the prescribed procedures. Furthermore, a daily and weekly hygiene schedule should be developed and consistently implemented in all functional areas, including classrooms, restrooms, and surrounding facilities. Restroom floors are recommended to be covered with non-slip, water-resistant materials to ensure dryness and eliminate unpleasant odors, thereby maintaining a safe and healthy environment for children.

The organization of children's meals should follow a scientifically structured plan to ensure nutritional adequacy and safety. Weekly menus must include all four essential food groups, avoiding any reduction or substitution of low-quality dishes compared with the approved plan. Preschool institutions are encouraged to publicly disclose daily food expenditures to parents and strictly prohibit any misuse of meal funds. Children should be served meals immediately after completing personal hygiene routines, and mealtime safety must be prioritized for example, ensuring food is not excessively hot and that children are not forced to eat rapidly or while crying, lying down, or standing.

In addition, institutions must comply fully with national regulations on food hygiene and safety, particularly regarding the procurement, preparation, and storage of food. Creating a safe and hygienic living and learning environment is equally important. Classrooms should be well-ventilated, adequately lit, and free from humidity and disease vectors such as flies, mosquitoes, or rodents. Furniture must be age-appropriate and ergonomically designed, and children should be provided with sufficient personal items to ensure comfort and well-being.

Teachers create all conditions and many opportunities for children to develop through activities, communication, and play. Do not impose or force children into the discipline without a voluntary or inappropriate educational element with the psychophysiological characteristics of children. Teachers must respect the children, do not offend the child's body and dignity in any way. Teachers and employees are periodically examined for health as prescribed.

Determining the detailed and specific contents in the activities of supporting the care and education of children in public preschools is very necessary and has important significance for management activities. Because, if the issues are not clearly identified, the activities of supporting children will hardly achieve good results. Burger [28] stated, "strict implementation of food safety regulations, absolutely safe learning environment, diverse and adequate learning spaces are prerequisites and necessary factors for educational activities in preschools."

4.3. The current situation of managing activities to ensure the quality of care and education

Determining the quality of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city is an important factor in evaluating the school's educational quality. Several researches [26], [28], [29] have shown the need to improve quality of support activities for child care and education in public kindergartens. To accurately assess the quality of support activities for child care and education in public kindergartens in Thu Duc city, the author surveyed 175 people, from March to July 2024. The survey results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 shows that most of the people surveyed, who are managers and teachers, highly appreciate the quality assurance of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city. Specifically, 70.0% of administrators and 54.66% of teachers rated it as good; no administrators and teachers rated it as weak. However, there are still 5.0% of managers and 6.67% of teachers with an average rating. Particularly for pupils' parents, 3.75% rated it as weak, 16.25% rated it as average, 37.5% rated it as good. The results of this study are similar to the research and evaluation results of [5], [21], [26], [27]. Although the data are slightly different due to different research time and space. However, the assessments obtained from the research results have shown that the management activities to support the care and education of children in public preschools in Thu Duc city are very important. However, the weaknesses in this activity also show that solutions are needed to improve the effectiveness of this activity.

The evaluation results combined with the conclusions of previous studies show the importance of supporting activities for child care and education. However, there are still incorrect perceptions about this activity. The survey results have set requirements for public preschools in Thu Duc city to have management measures to further improve activities to ensure the quality of child care and education, contributing to improving the quality of preschool education in Thu Duc city.

Table 1. Evaluation of the quality of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city

Order	Object of survey	Quantity	Total (%)	Degree evaluation							
				Weak		Medium		Rather		Good	
				Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%
1	Managers	20	100	0	0.0	1	5.00	5	25.00	14	70.00
2	Teacher	75	100	0	0.0	5	6.67	29	38.67	41	54.66
3	Pupils' parents	80	100	3	3.75	13	16.25	30	37.50	34	42.50

Determining the content of ensuring the quality of child care and education in public preschools in Thu Duc city is indispensable content in ensuring the quality of child care and education. Determining the content of ensuring the quality of child care and education in public preschools in Thu Duc city is indispensable content in ensuring the quality of child care and education. Previous research [26]–[28] has shown the diversity in the content of support activities for child care and education in public kindergartens. To accurately assess the content of support activities for child care and education in public kindergartens in Thu Duc city, the author surveyed 175 people. The survey results are shown in Table 2.

The survey results in Table 2 show that, all three survey subjects (administrators, teachers, and pupils' parents) assessed the concentration at a good and rather physical development (50.86%–45.14%), quality assurance of language use and communication (49.72%–45.71%), and quality assurance of cognitive ability (48.57%–45.14%) is good. Particularly with other contents: quality assurance of emotional development and life skills (45.71%–46.86%) and quality assurance of aesthetic development (42.86%–47.43%) is good. As for the content assuring the quality of aesthetic development, some still rate it as weak. The average rating ranges from 4.00% to 8.57% in all survey contents.

The survey results in Table 2 show that, for many years, even public preschools in Thu Duc city have made many efforts to improve the quality of education in general and the quality of educational care in particular. However, the quality of activities still has some limitations. This shows the need for appropriate solutions to improve activities further to ensure the quality of child care and education in public preschools in Thu Duc city in all content in the coming time.

Theoretical and practical studies have shown that for activities to achieve good results, basic conditions are needed. In activities supporting the care and education of preschool children, the basic conditions are facilities, financial resources, teachers, staff, and education program; this is the basic and important factors for successful operations. To assess the current status of conditions for quality assurance activities of child care and education at public preschools, the author conducted a survey of 175 people from March to July 2024, which the rating convention is as: 1 (poor); 2 (weak); 3 (medium); 4 (rather); 5 (good). The specific results are shown in Table 3.

In the assessment of service conditions activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools, administrators, teachers, and pupils' parents were assessed on four criteria: facilities and teaching equipment; teacher and staff; educational program; and finance. The highest percentage is concentrated at level 4 (equivalent to a good rating), which is the highest. In each specific criterion, there are also not positive evaluations from administrators, teachers, and parents, especially the content: "There are outdoor areas to be organized. giving children experimental activities," the excellent rating is 30.86%, the lowest in the assessed contents of teaching facilities and equipment. Similarly, the percentage of content rated creative in educational program also reached 30.86% with a good rating. In the section teachers and staff, the content teachers and staff are regularly fostered with a good rating of 34.86%. Particularly, the content "enough finance for outdoor educational activities for children" has the highest average rating of 32.57%. With these problems, it is necessary to take measures to improve and overcome the conditions for service quality assurance of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city.

Table 2. The actual situation of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city

Order	Object of survey	Quantity	Total (%)	Degree evaluation							
				Weak		Medium		Rather		Good	
				Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%
1	Quality assurance of physical development	175	100	0	0.0	7	4.00	79	45.14	89	50.86
2	Quality assurance in language use and communication	175	100	0	0.0	8	4.57	80	45.71	87	49.72
3	Quality assurance of cognitive ability	175	100	0	0.0	11	6.29	79	45.14	85	48.57
4	Quality assurance of emotional development and life skills	175	100	0	0.0	13	7.43	82	46.86	80	45.71
5	Quality assurance of aesthetic development	175	100	2	1.14	15	8.57	83	47.43	75	42.86

Table 3. Current status of conditions for quality assurance of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city

Order	Survey content	Rating level (number of people)									
		1		2		3		4		5	
		F	R (%)	F	R (%)	F	R (%)	F	R (%)	F	R (%)
1	Teaching facilities and equipment										
1.1	Having enough land or floor area as prescribed, the school's buildings are built solidly or semi-permanently	0	0.00	7	4.00	14	8.00	87	49.71	67	38.29
1.2	The playground area is planned and designed appropriately, with green trees to create shade	0	0.00	8	4.57	14	8.00	88	50.29	65	37.14
1.3	There is a dedicated garden for children to take care of, to help them explore and learn	2	1.14	8	4.57	16	9.14	89	50.86	60	34.29
1.4	The outdoor children's play area is tiled, cemented, or planted with grass, with toys according to regulations	2	1.14	9	5.14	15	8.57	89	50.86	60	34.29
1.5	There are outdoor areas for children to experiment	3	2.29	10	5.71	17	9.71	90	51.43	54	30.86
	Average total	1.60	0.91	8.40	4.80	15.2	8.69	88.6	50.63	61.2	34.97
2	Team of teachers and staff										
2.1	The full team of teachers and staff	0	0.0	8	4.57	15	8.57	89	50.86	63	36.00
2.2	Teachers and staff are trained regularly	0	0.0	9	5.14	14	8.00	91	52.00	61	34.86
	Average total	0	0.0	8.50	4.86	14.5	8.27	90	51.43	62	35.44
3	Education program										
3.1	Follow the preschool education program	0	0.0	8	4.57	17	9.71	89	50.86	61	34.86
3.2	There is creativity	0	0.0	12	6.86	19	10.86	90	51.42	54	30.86
	Average total	0	0.0	10	5.71	18	10.29	89.5	51.14	57.5	32.86
4	Finance										
4.1	Sufficient finance for outdoor educational activities for children	4	2.29	37	21.14	57	32.57	50	28.57	27	15.43
4.2	Financial resources are used appropriately, thriftily, and without waste	0	0.0	10	13.33	17	9.71	79	45.14	69	39.43
	Average total	2	1.15	23.5	17.24	37	21.14	64.5	36.86	48	27.43

Note: F=Frequency, R=Ratio

4.4. Results of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools

According to the survey results, the contents of management activities ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools is highly appreciated. There were 77.14% of respondents rated the development of an action plan to ensure the quality of child care and education in public preschools as good or fairly good. This planning activity is regarded as a fundamental element that underpins the effective implementation of child care and educational support programs. In the absence of a clearly defined plan, subsequent activities may lack direction, thereby hindering the achievement of the intended outcomes.

The implementation of planned activities to ensure the quality of child care and education in public preschools was rated as good or fairly good by 75.43% of respondents. According to experts, implementation refers to the process of translating planned objectives into concrete actions. The generally positive evaluation indicates that this activity has been given considerable attention and is being executed effectively in most institutions. However, 24.57% of participants still rated the implementation as average or poor, suggesting that the quality of execution remains uneven across preschools.

The directing and supervision of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education in public preschools were rated as good or fairly good by 78.86% of respondents. Similarly, 69.14% evaluated the inspection and assessment activities as good or fairly good. However, more than one-fourth of participants still rated these activities as poor, indicating that the management, control, and supervision processes in some institutions remain limited. This finding suggests that public preschools in Thu Duc city should adopt timely and systematic measures to enhance the effectiveness of their monitoring and quality assurance practices.

The management of essential conditions such as facilities, teaching equipment, financial resources, human resources, and educational programs for ensuring the quality of child care and education in public preschools was rated as fairly good by 68.57% of respondents. This aspect received the lowest rating among all management areas assessed. The findings indicate that, although attention has been given to this domain in recent years, the measures implemented to mobilize and utilize resources for supporting child care and educational activities in preschools have not yet demonstrated sufficient effectiveness.

The survey results have shown that, in recent years, the management of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city was taken care of and done well. However, there are still some limitations that need to be overcome. In the new situation, to meet the requirements of a comprehensive new management education, and have appropriate solutions and it is necessary to continue to innovate and constantly improve the quality of education at the preschool level.

4.5. Cause of the situation

Table 4 reveals several key factors influencing the management of child care and education in preschools. These include the perceptions of management staff in public preschools, teachers' professional awareness, leadership and guidance from superior authorities, financial and facility conditions, teaching staff and early childhood education programs, as well as the perceptions of parents and the broader community. Collectively, these factors received over 90% of responses rating them as good or fairly good. The findings highlight the critical role of teachers and parents, whose direct interactions significantly shape children's learning and care experiences in preschool settings. Furthermore, the awareness of management staff in public preschools and the role of state management agencies in education were also highly valued, with over 85% of respondents rating them positively. As the entities responsible for formulating, directing, and implementing policies and activities in early childhood care and education, these organizations play a central and highly recognized role in ensuring quality practice at the preschool level.

Table 4. Causes of the actual situation of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city (from March to July 2024)

Order	Object of survey	Quantity	Degree evaluation							
			Weak		Medium		Rather		Good	
			Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%	Quantity	%
1	Awareness of management staff of public preschools	175	3	1.71	21	12.00	82	46.86	69	39.43
2	Perceptions of teachers and staff of public preschools	175	0	0.0	8	4.57	81	46.29	86	49.14
3	Perception of pupils' parents and society	175	0	0.0	8	4.57	80	45.71	87	49.72
4	Financial condition and facilities; teachers and staff; preschool education program	175	0	0.0	13	7.43	82	46.86	80	45.71
5	Leadership and direction of superiors.	175	3	1.71	20	11.43	83	47.43	69	39.43

4.6. Some operational measures to ensure the quality of child care and education

First of all, it is essential to organize awareness-raising initiatives among managers and teachers regarding the necessity of quality assurance activities in child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city. These initiatives should focus on thoroughly understanding the key resolutions of the Party, the State, the Ministry of Education and Training, and the Ho Chi Minh city authorities concerning the fundamental and comprehensive renovation of education and training. Through this process, management staff and teachers can gain a deeper understanding of the purposes, significance, and values of quality assurance in preschool child care and education within the competency-based approach. At the same time, such initiatives should promote awareness of individual roles and responsibilities in fostering school development and enhancing professional reputation.

For the management team, it is necessary to have a solid understanding of the position, function, the role of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education. With good awareness, new managers can make the right decisions to direct employees to set goals, plans, implement plans, and evaluate results as well as make necessary adjustments [12]. At the same time, constantly improving management skills will help managers of public kindergartens constantly innovate in managing the school's educational activities.

For teachers, raising awareness about quality assurance activities about the position, role, and function of the quality assurance activities in child care and education will help teachers improve the results of their child-rearing work [6], [19]. Continuous learning, improving experience and educational skills are also mandatory factors for the teaching staff. From there, support the right time and the right needs of the child with the best quality possible.

For parents of pupils, it is necessary to raise awareness about quality assurance activities for children's education and care, which is one of the most effective ways for parents to understand more about their children's needs, how to take care of their children, and how to care for child education of them; be aware of the support parents can receive from quality assurance in their child's education [19], [28]. Raising awareness of pupils' parents will improve the results of cooperation between schools and families in the care and education of children. At the same time, parents themselves need to develop a childcare plan as well as a coordination plan with the school.

Second, it is necessary to promote innovation in planning activities to ensure the quality of child care and education in public preschools in Thu Duc city. A key component of this process is assessing children's needs through close collaboration with parents, as understanding children's developmental characteristics and family expectations forms a crucial foundation for establishing appropriate goals and action plans. This innovative approach enables schools to design child-centered educational programs that better reflect actual needs and promote comprehensive development. In preschool, the element of satisfying children's needs is the focus and top priority. Assessing the needs of young children allows administrators and teachers to have a better view of the needs and categorize children according to the school's ability to meet them [5], [11]. Based on the needs of the child, consider the ability to meet to conduct the development of educational goals and educational plans to achieve those goals. This assessment must be done regularly. It can be assessed through each semester, each school year; or assessed through the completion of assigned tasks. This assessment must be based on state regulations on the provision of facilities for learners. At the same time, assess the suitability of the facilities provided for future additions.

An overall assessment of the school's essential resources for implementing the resource mobilization plan and for ensuring the efficient and economical use of these resources is required. These include financial capital and the support provided by social organizations. The assessment should be undertaken by the functional departments of Thu Duc city, particularly the Department of Education. Responsibilities and timelines must be clearly defined, and an annual review should be conducted to evaluate teachers' performance against the established plan. This entire activity needs to be deployed synchronously to all managers, teachers, staff and parents of students in the entire school.

Third, it is essential to strengthen the direction and supervision of activities to ensure the quality of child care and education in public preschools in Thu Duc city. Specifically, management should provide clear guidance for teachers to design lessons aligned with new requirements, organize educational care activities, review practical experiences, and identify effective solutions to emerging challenges. Strengthen the management of teachers' class time; organize children's learning activities through time attendance, class visits, and seminars, ensuring correct and adequate teaching of program content and organizing activities according to the educational plan of the group or class.

It is necessary to regularly monitor and evaluate the educational activities of teachers to ensure quality and effectiveness. This process includes reviewing teachers' planning, examining lesson plans and teaching hours, assessing the use of teaching equipment and information technology applications, as well as evaluating the extent to which teachers engage in learning, training, and improving their professional knowledge and skills. Directing professional groups to organize periodic activities to learn from experience, promptly detect errors and deviations in educational activities, encourage teachers with good achievements,

and develop working regulations. The work is reasonable in terms of time, but the content of activities is scientific and inefficient.

Fourth, it is necessary to reform the inspection and evaluation process to ensure the quality of child care and education. This process should include the development of evaluation criteria covering aspects such as plan implementation, children's progress, collaboration among colleagues, and relationships with families and community stakeholders. Evaluation criteria need to have a specific scale expressed in points. There is need to be steps to evaluate the scale to suit the conditions of each preschool.

Regularly check and evaluate all active content in various forms of flexible testing and evaluation, suitable for specific audiences and content. Identifying strengths and discovering weaknesses is very important to help school administrators have appropriate management measures. From the test results, re-evaluate and re-verify the accuracy and effectiveness of the measures to have solutions to adjust and overcome shortcomings and errors and promote strengths.

Fifth, it is essential to strengthen the conditions that ensure the quality of child care and education. This involves conducting regular inspections and assessments of the quantity, quality, and needs related to facilities, equipment, and teaching materials, thereby developing plans for additional procurement and timely repair. Materials and devices used for teaching, supervision, and learning should be maintained in good condition and effectively utilized to enhance children's capacity. Teachers should be encouraged to apply modern teaching aids and information technology in educational activities. Furthermore, the management and preservation of facilities and equipment must be reinforced to minimize damage, ensure sustainability, and support continuous improvement in teaching and learning quality. Exploiting and applying information technology, designing teaching contents suitable to the school's facilities and equipment.

Mobilize socialization resources for activities to ensure the quality of child care and education [29]. It is necessary to develop specific plans for "socialization" activities and coordination between schools and families. These plans should be disseminated at the beginning of each academic year, and any changes must be promptly communicated to relevant stakeholders. The effective use of budgeted financial resources, the professional development of teachers and educational staff [30], the mobilization and lawful utilization of additional financial resources [14], [31], the strengthening of international cooperation in education [32], and the application of science and technology in school management [33] constitute fundamental factors contributing to the effectiveness of child care and education support activities, thereby meeting the growing demands of a rapidly developing society.

5. CONCLUSION

The results show that child care and education activities and management activities ensure the quality of child care and education at public preschools in Thu Duc city is a necessary job, especially in the integration trend, the development of science and technology, the development of the knowledge economy in the world, and the comprehensive renovation of our country's education. The actual situation of quality assurance of child care and education and management of quality assurance of child care and education at public preschools has been approved by the Department of Education and Training of Thu Duc city. Public preschool in Thu Duc city has achieved many encouraging results in recent years. Activities to support child care and education and manage activities to support child care and education at public preschools have contributed to improving the quality of preschool education; a reputation for the education industry of Thu Duc city in particular and the whole of Ho Chi Minh city. Due to limitations in management, there are still some shortcomings in the support activities care and education of children in public preschools according to the quality assurance approach; the management efficiency as well as the performance results in some contents of the activities to ensure the quality of child care and education have not yet achieved the expected results. The proposed management measures partly assist managers in referencing existing practices and developing new initiatives to achieve continuous improvement. This is just the initial result of the research, the number of surveys is not much, the experimental solution needs time to continue the research.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This study was conducted with consent from the survey participants. We would like to sincerely thank the interviewees and respondents for agreeing to respond and providing objective assessments.

FUNDING INFORMATION

This research did not receive any funding from any organization.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Thuan Van Pham	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓
LongAn Dang Nguyen	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Derived data supporting the findings of this study are available from Ministry of Education and Training, Circular No. 01/VBHN-BGDĐT, April 13, 2021, promulgating preschool education program. Hanoi, Vietnam, 2021, <https://moet.gov.vn/van-ban/vanban/Pages/chi-tiet-van-ban.aspx?ItemID=1400>.

REFERENCES

- [1] Communist Party of Vietnam, "The XIIIth National Delegation Congress," National Politics, Hanoi (in Vietnamese), 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://tulieuvankien.dangcongsan.vn/ban-chap-hanh-trung-uong-dang/dai-hoi-dang/lan-thu-xiii/dai-hoi-dai-bieu-toan-quoc-lan-thu-xiii-cua-dang-cong-san-viet-nam-3660>
- [2] L. T. Luan, "Evaluating the implementation of the child care and education plan in preschools to ensure gender equality and suitability to local contexts," *Vietnam Journal of Educational Sciences*, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 52–57, 2022.
- [3] Institute of Linguistics, *Vietnamese dictionary*. Hanoi: Encyclopedia Publisher, 2021.
- [4] C. M. Itin, "Reasserting the philosophy of experiential education as a vehicle for change in the 21st century," *Journal of Experiential Education*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 91–98, Sep. 1999, doi: 10.1177/105382599902200206.
- [5] A. L. McGowan, M. C. Chandler, and H. K. Gerde, "Infusing physical activity into early childhood classrooms: Guidance for best practices," *Early Childhood Education Journal*, vol. 52, no. 8, pp. 2021–2038, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s10643-023-01532-5.
- [6] V. H. Van, "Ensuring the quality of education and training in the context of educational innovation," *Quality - Access to Success*, vol. 25, no. 198, pp. 40–50, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.47750/QAS/25.198.05.
- [7] A. De Vincenzi, A. Garau, and A. Guaglianone, "Has the quality of teaching and learning processes improved as a result of the implementation of quality assurance coordinated by the state?" *Quality in Higher Education*, vol. 24, no. 1, pp. 55–65, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1080/13538322.2018.1426382.
- [8] Ministry of Education and Training, "Circular 6/2025/TT-BGDĐT, Circular Amending and supplementing several articles in the Regulations on university and college admissions for Preschool Education issued together with Circular No. 08/2022/TT-BGDĐT dated June 6, 2022 of the Minister of Education and Training." (in Vietnamese), 2025.
- [9] Ho Chi Minh City People's Council, "Resolution No. 12/2024/NQ-HDND regulating tuition fees for public preschool and general education from 2024 - 2025 and subsequent years in Ho Chi Minh City." (in Vietnamese), 2024.
- [10] D. R. Becker and P. A. Nader, "Run fast and sit still: Connections among aerobic fitness, physical activity, and sedentary time with executive function during pre-kindergarten," *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, vol. 57, pp. 1–11, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ecresq.2021.04.007.
- [11] National Assembly, "Law on Education (Law No. 43/2019/QH14)," Hanoi, 2020.
- [12] H. Hoduc, H. Vothanh, and V. Vuhong, "The changes in education policy in the context of educational innovation in Vietnam," *Revista on line de Política e Gestão Educacional*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 1–16, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.22633/rpge.v26iesp.1.16772.
- [13] L. T. Hang and V. H. Van, "Building strong teaching and learning strategies through teaching innovations and learners' creativity: A study of Vietnam universities," *International Journal of Education and Practice*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 498–510, 2020, doi: 10.18488/journal.61.2020.83.498.510.
- [14] V. Vu Hong, "Management of educational activities in schools towards the approach of learners' competency: a case study of a high school," *Nuances: Estudos sobre Educação*, vol. 32, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.32930/nuances.v32i00.9118.
- [15] Ministry of Education and Training, "Circular No. 01/VBHN-BGDĐT, promulgating preschool education program," Hanoi (in Vietnamese), 2021.
- [16] Ministry of Education and Training, "Preschool education program document according to circular No. 01/2021," Ministry of Education and Training, Hanoi, 2021.
- [17] The Party Central Committee, *Resolution on fundamental and comprehensive renovation in education*. Hanoi, Vietnam, 2013, 2013.
- [18] P. V. Thuan and D. N. Longan, *Handbook on quality accreditation of preschool and general education*. Hanoi: Education Publisher, 2022.
- [19] V. H. Van, T. T. Thanh, and N. T. H. Hoa, "Enhancing learning interesting for students: influencing factors and proposed solutions," *Multidisciplinary Science Journal*, vol. 5, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.31893/multiscience.2023066.

- [20] J. Stang-Rabrig, T. Brüggemann, R. Lorenz, and N. McElvany “Teachers’ occupational well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic: The role of resources and demands,” *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 117, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2022.103803.
- [21] Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), *Providing quality early childhood education and care: results from the starting strong survey 2018*. Paris: OECD Publishing, 2019, doi: 10.1787/301005d1-en.
- [22] H. Du, R. B. King, and P. Chi, “Self-esteem and subjective well-being revisited: The roles of personal, relational, and collective self-esteem,” *PLoS ONE*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 1–17, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0183958.
- [23] V. Luongngoc and V. Vuhong, “The educational role of social media in policy communication in Vietnam,” (in Portuguese), *Revista on line de Política e Gestão Educacional*, vol. 26, no. 1, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.22633/rpge.v26iesp.1.16513.
- [24] L. Holopainen, K. Waltzer, N. Hoang, K. Lappalainen, H. Nuutinen, and H. Pesonen, “The role of educational support in the development of subjective well-being in Finnish general upper secondary education,” *Psychology in the Schools*, vol. 60, no. 8, pp. 2795–2808, 2023, doi: 10.1002/pits.22885.
- [25] V. Vu Hong, “Necessity and solutions for ethical education among teachers in the framework of industrial revolution 4.0,” *Revista on line de Política e Gestão Educacional*, vol. 26, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.22633/rpge.v26i00.17731.
- [26] N. T. Nga, N. T. N. Minh, and N. T. Trang, “Needs, conditions and possibilities of applying digital technology to child care and education at preschools in industrial parks and export processing zones: a case study in Binh Tan district, Ho Chi Minh city,” (in Vietnamese), *Journal of Education*, vol. 22, no. 11, pp. 27–32, 2022.
- [27] N. T. Huyen, “Some research on organizing play activities for students of preschool education major in the current period,” (in Vietnamese), *Vietnam Journal of Educational Sciences*, vol. 5, pp. 81–87, 2021.
- [28] K. Burger, “Effective early childhood care and education: Successful approaches and didactic strategies for fostering child development,” *European Early Childhood Education Research Journal*, vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 743–760, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1080/1350293X.2014.882076.
- [29] F. Söderholm, K. Lappalainen, L. Holopainen, and J. Viljaranta, “The development of school burnout in general upper secondary education: the role of support and schoolwork difficulties,” *Educational Psychology*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 607–625, 2022, doi: 10.1080/01443410.2022.2054954.
- [30] D. Hiep and H. V. Van, “Buildingg and developing a teacher team from a perspective of legal policy and practice,” *Revista Juridica*, vol. 2, no. 78, pp. 545–572, 2024, doi: 10.26668/revistajur.2316-753X.v2i78.6871.
- [31] C. Céspedes, A. Rubio, F. Viñas, S. M. Cerrato, E. Lara-Órdenes, and J. Ríos, “Relationship between self-concept, self-efficacy, and subjective well-being of native and migrant adolescents,” *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 11, pp. 1–11, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2020.620782.
- [32] N. S. Trung and V. H. Van, “Vietnamese education identity in the process of international integration,” *Journal of Advances in Education and Philosophy*, vol. 04, no. 05, pp. 220–225, May 2020, doi: 10.36348/jaep.2020.v04i05.006.
- [33] P. V Thuan and D. N. AnLong, *Management of educational accreditation of lower secondary colleges in the context of educational innovation*. Hanoi: Education, 2021.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Thuan Van Pham is an associate professor at the Academy of Educational Management, holding the position of director. Dr. Thuan participates in teaching undergraduate and postgraduate students and supervising master’s and doctoral students. Research directions are educational, educational management, innovation, and creativity in education. The author has had many articles published in prestigious scientific journals (listed in Scopus and WoS) and has published many monographs and textbooks for teaching. His major interest is to continue to focus on educational issues and educational administration in universities. He has received many certificates of merit from the Ministry of Education and Training and Hanoi National University for management, teaching and research activities. He can be contacted at email: thuanpv@vnu.edu.vn.

LongAn Dang Nguyen is vice principal of Ho Chi Minh City College of Economics. She earned a doctorate in educational management in 2021 at the Military and Political Academy of Vietnam. Previously, she worked as chief of staff of the Department of Education of Ho Chi Minh City (the largest economic center in the country). In 2022, she was appointed as Vice Principal of Ho Chi Minh city College of Economics. She participates in teaching and guiding graduate students and graduate students at many Vietnamese universities. She has had many articles in the fields of education, educational management, psychology, learning, and teaching methods. Her major interest is to continue to focus on educational issues and educational administration in colleges and universities. She has received many certificates of merit from the Ho Chi Minh City People’s Committee for her management, teaching and research activities. She can be contacted at email: longnda@kthcm.edu.vn.